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CENTRE FOR
DEVELOPMENT
POLICY AND
PRACTICE

EDUCATION QUALITY: HOW DO WE GET BETTER OUTCOMES FROM OUR SCHOOLS

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In collaboration with

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INTRODUCTION

India's education sector is indeed in a bad state. There are serious problems with respect to access to education itself, and quality education is simply not available. 89% of kids of primary school-going age of the richest 20 per cent of the population attend school both in the rural and urban areas, while that proportion drops to 79% for kids in the poorest fifth of the population in rural areas and 78% in urban areas. But, attendance drops sharply when it comes to secondary school and becomes worse at the higher secondary level. Also, the difference between the richest and the poorest in enrolment widens sharply from the primary section to the secondary and higher educational levels.

The gulf between the poor and the rich widens as we go up the ladder. Only 6% of young people from the bottom 20 per cent of the population attend educational levels above higher secondary in urban India, while 31% among the richest 20 per cent of the population attend secondary school. The middle class is also substantially disadvantaged when it comes to higher education. The situation is substantially worse in rural India. What happens, therefore is that the richer children have much better opportunities for higher education, essential for getting good jobs in the cities. These are also the children who travel abroad for jobs and for higher education. The poorer children must then work in the informal sector at low wages and remain vulnerable.

Muslims have the highest percentage of illiterates aged beyond seven years at 42.72%, as compared to 36.40% among Hindus, 32.49% among Sikhs, 28.17% among Buddhists and 25.66% among Christians. Jains have the highest percentage of literates above seven years of age among India's religious communities, with Census India 2011 finding 86.73% of them as literate and only 13.57% as illiterate. As per the latest data released on 'education level by the religious community for age seven and above' by the government, other minority communities score over both Hindus and Muslims in literacy levels. As compared to 63.60% of Hindus and 57.28% Muslims in the 'literate' category, the percentage of literates among Christians is 74.34%, among Buddhists 71.83% and among Sikhs 67.51%.

What is indeed sad is that across the country, 29 per cent of children drop out before completing five years of primary school, and 43 per cent before finishing upper primary school. Only 42 per cent get to complete high school.

This ensures that India stands among the top five nations for out-of-school children of primary school age, with 1.4 million children in the age group 6 to 11-year-olds not attending school. What does not help at all is that a number of schools are not equipped to handle the complete population. There is a teacher shortage of 689,000 teachers in primary schools. Just about 53 percent of schools have functional girls' toilets, and 74 per cent have access to drinking water.

Some states have wide gender differences at the secondary levels. For instance, net attendance rates at the secondary level in Gujarat is 63% for boys and 43% for girls. Gujarat is one of India's most industrialised states but shows some strange results on how girls are treated there. The sex ratio in Gujarat came down to 919 in 2011 from 920 in 2001 as against a significant increase of 10 points in the national average during this period. As against the national figure of 943, the overall sex ratio of Gujarat was 919 in 2011. Sex ratio is the number of girls to every 1000 boys in the population. A low sex ratio indicates very high levels of discrimination against the female gender.

Going back to education, the difference between scheduled castes and tribes and other categories widens at higher levels of education. It is particularly large for urban girls belonging to scheduled tribes

at the secondary and higher secondary levels. Enrolment of Muslims is lower compared to those of other religions at every level, both for males and females. In urban India, while enrolment for Muslim boys in primary schools is only marginally lower, the proportion at the higher educational levels is substantially lower. Muslim girls enrol in comparable numbers in primary schools, but the drop-out rates at secondary levels are alarming,

Much of this can be attributed to the low levels of expenditure on education. According to the World Bank indicators, government expenditure on education as a percentage of gross domestic product was 3.8% for India in 2012. Compared to other poor countries it is abysmally low. The figure is 6.3% for Vietnam, 4.3% for Mali, 4.7% for Nepal and 5% for Rwanda. As a result, the state is unable to provide education infrastructure to a large number of the poor. It also results in primary schools rarely getting upgraded to secondary levels, forcing a number of our children to stop studying after primary levels as they are not able to travel long distances to continue their education. What is simply inexplicable is the state building primary schools after the Right to Education Act has been passed. The RTE mandates compulsory education for children in the 6 to 14 age groups. How then can it justify making schools only for the 6 to 10- year-olds? What the RTE now implies is that there cannot be stand-alone primary schools anywhere, and certainly not in areas where there are no other schools. All primary schools must immediately be converted to secondary schools.

Lastly, there is one rather disturbing feature in this data. While Jains are the most literate groups in the country, it is distressing that the girl child is treated badly. Sikhs and Jains have the worst sex ratio in the country, as per additional census data. According to the 2011 census, there were 828 girls in the age of 0 to 6 years in the Sikh community in comparison to 1,000 boys. Among the Jains, there were 889 girls against 1,000 boys in the age group of 0 to 6 years. The child sex ratio of the total population in the country was 918 girls against 1,000 boys. Education does not seem to help the gender divide among our most educated communities.

With a middle-class population exceeding 300 million, India is the largest market for automobiles, high- value foods, mobile phones etc., ahead of or just behind China. This turnaround has happened as education levels have gone up - nearly 98% of children are enrolled in primary schools now. Another reason is the fall in fertility rates, where now an average Indian family has less than three children compared to five, a couple of decades ago, leading to increased expense on education and healthier child. There is enough debate on this now. Are demographics India's biggest challenge, as argued in the Economist's cover story¹, or do they give India the opportunity for a truly knowledge-based economy it looks for? If India is to seize new opportunities that the new millennium brings², it will have to overhaul its higher education sector. The key to it is to create a large number of skilled people year after year. Nearly 10 million youth will join the workforce every year for at least another decade, and to skill them will take a gigantic effort.

The sobering facts are rather dramatic. Even now, India is far behind all developed and even most developing countries. According to the 2011 census, the literacy rate has reached 74%, which means that even now, 25% of the population remains completely unlettered. At the tertiary level, in terms of our children seeking university education, the Gross Enrolment Ratio is an abysmal 16%, while the world average is over 27%. Only 17 million children have access to university seats. Even now, only about

1 The Economist, May 11, 2013.

2 Scott argues that the challenges facing higher education in the new millennium cannot be understood unless proper account is taken of the phenomenon of globalisation. Scott, P. (2000).

15% of our children matriculate, and just half the number ever reach college. According to a 2011 India's Planning Commission sponsored study, the deficit in the number of seats in school had reached 60 million. This means that 60 million children in India today don't have a school seat even if they want to attend school. At the university level, this means that if just 30% attend university, at least 36 million more seats need to be created. With a total number of about 900 universities now, India still needs double the number.

India still shows remarkably high inequality in terms of access to education and health facilities³. For India to sustain the growth momentum and achieve greater heights in education and economy sector, it is imperative that it builds institutions that skill the large numbers of youth entering the labour markets every year. A new beginning from early stages of life, redrawn primary education pedagogies, a lesser emphasis on examinations, trained teachers and significantly higher incentives to research are what the education sector for tomorrow needs.

METHODOLOGY

The primary aim of the study was to assess what brings quality to school education. The study looks at what makes certain schools attract and retain students. For the purpose of analysing this, the project was divided into two components.

In the first part, experts in the field of education were consulted. Their perceptions and experiences on various aspects of education were transcribed and analysed qualitatively.

- Farhad Merchant
- Gowri Iswaran
- Jyotsana Brar
- Kiran Bir Sethi
- Meeta W Sengupta
- Pankaj Jain
- Pankaj Tripathi
- Rekha Dey
- Ritesh Singh
- Romana Shaikh
- Sameen Fatima
- Tarun
- Umme Salma

For the second part, the team at CDPP spoke to school administrators, directors and teachers in Hyderabad, covering various boards, curriculums and management. The idea was to look at each school's journey to understand their strengths, weaknesses and challenges. Each of those learnings

³ The Human Development Report cautions that even now about 1.6 billion people, 30 per cent of the population in the 104 developing and poor countries, live in poor conditions. It also states that income inequality has been going up in many countries of the world. While overall inequality has marginally declined in the last two decades, it is the inequality on health and education that has grown. Sub Saharan Africa for example, shows the highest inequality in terms of access to health and health indicators, while South Asia shows the highest inequality in terms of access to education and educational achievements.

have been put together in a case study format. The analysis helps us to arrive at what essentially makes a good school.

- Al Falah School
- Azaan International School
- Chowraha Jinsi Govt. Primary School
- Creekside International School
- Focus High School
- Glendale International School
- Hyderabad Public School
- Iqra Mission High School
- Madina Public School
- Mount Mercy School
- Princess Esin Girls' High School

The study has used a combination of primary and secondary data. The data has been analysed qualitatively.

WHAT BRINGS QUALITY TO EDUCATION?

This section of the report is based on the inputs received by individuals who have left an indelible footprint in the field of education. These experts have provided insights on various aspects of education that bring quality in the process and outcome. The perceptions and narratives of the following people have been used to define the elements that make up for an effective education system:

- **Farhad Merchant** has 25+ years of versatile experience in the corporate and social sectors, with international exposure, having worked with clients from various countries and sectors/industries. As CEO at Aga Khan Education Service (AKES), India, he drives organisational change and the school improvement agenda. He is responsible for the India portfolio, focused on bringing in best practices and educational excellence across all units to achieve effective student learning outcomes.
- **Gowri Iswaran** is the recipient of the coveted Padmashri Award from the Govt. of India in 2004. She is an innovative educationist with over 30 years of experience in leading schools of India. She has been the Founder Principal of Sanskriti School, New Delhi. She is currently the Vice Chairman of The Global Education and Leadership Foundation. She is also on the Advisory Board of the Shiv Nadar Foundation.
- **Jyotsana Brar** is Member of the CBSE and the Examinations Committee of the Council for the ICSE. Governing Council Member for The Latika Roy Foundation and 'Raphael' Ryder Cheshire Home. Member of the Board and the Academics Committee of the Himjyoti School Dehradun, a residential school for girls from economically weaker families of different districts of Uttarakhand. Recipient of the Pride of Uttarakhand Award, the Indian Public Schools Conference Lifetime Achievement Award and the NDTV-Educomp Lifetime Achievement Award.
- **Kiran Bir Sethi** is an Indian designer, educationist, education reformer, and social entrepreneur. She founded the award-winning Riverside School in Ahmedabad that focuses on empowering children with the I CAN MINDSET – nourished with humane values. She then founded aProCh (an

initiative to make our cities more child friendly) and finally Design for Change which is today the one of the largest movements of change – for and by the children. Today, DFC is in more than 60 countries – and children use the simple design thinking framework to design solutions for some of their greatest challenges.

- **Meeta W. Sengupta** is a Fellow of the Salzburg Global Seminar, and a Fellow of the Royal Society of Arts et al. Meeta has been the founder of the Centre for Education Strategy, a Delhi based think tank that builds bridges between policy and practice for educators, educationists and Institutions. She has been the Senior Advisor, Centre for Civil Society. She has been a member of the FICCI (Federation of Indian Chambers of Commerce and Industry) Skills Development Forum. She is the member Education Expert on the National Council of NISA (National Independent Schools Alliance) that represents over 6000 budget schools.
- **Pankaj Jain** is Founder-Chief Functionary of the Education Support Organisation, which runs Gyan Shala, an NGO that serves the educational needs of several districts across multiple districts in India. Gyan Shala is a unique model that seeks to educate children by focusing primarily on curriculum development, and thus reducing the costs associated with educating children. Jain works extensively with the Gyan Shala model in the slums of Ahmedabad and Bihar.
- **Pankaj Tripathi** is an ex-Civil Servant. After serving with the Government of India for 25 years (1993-2018) in different capacities within India and in Indian Diplomatic Missions abroad, including in Islamabad, Central Asia and Frankfurt. He has been working in the social sector since February 2019, as Principal Consultant with the Sarojini Damodaran Foundation (SDF) that supports the education of students from economically disadvantaged families.
- **Rekha Dey** is a sport and development specialist with over 19 years of experience. She has been a Member, Expert Reference Group for the development of a MOOC on sport, development and building peaceful and inclusive societies, an initiative of the Commonwealth Secretariat and the Australian government (2019-20). She has held various positions in the past. She was India Coordinator for the Australian Sports Outreach Program (ASOP), a 'Sport for Development' program of the Government of Australia (2012-15); She was Director at Sports Education Development Australia (2015-18), an Australian training provider in the fitness sector.
- **Ritesh Singh** is the co-founder of Eckovation. Eckovation had ensured the reach of quality education to more than 10 million students and projects of Eckovation won prestigious awards like Prime Minister's Excellence Award and Commonwealth International Innovation Award. During college, he also started a non-profit organisation, SARAS, to help the masses get access to education technology developed by universities in India and abroad. It was the time spent working with SARAS that urged him to join Avanti, a non-profit organisation that provides low-income high-school students with a world-class science and mathematics education.
- **Romana Shaikh** is a 2009 Teach for India alumnus, Romana served as the Director, Training & Impact team at Teach for India where she led large teams to expand the purpose and scope of educational outcome. Today, Romana coaches' schools globally with Kizazi, enabling them to innovate and design learning that is empowering of culture and diversity. Continuing her practice as a facilitator and community builder, she supports various initiatives, including the Thrive collaborative, The Mind Room and because you, a social enterprise for mental health.

- **Syeda Sameen Fatima** did her post-graduation from University of Massachusetts, USA and received her Doctorate in Computer Science & Engineering from Osmania University, Hyderabad. She has 37 years of rich teaching, research and administration experience from OU, UoH, BITS and University of Massachusetts at Amherst in USA.
- **Mohd. Suleman Siddiqui** is Former Vice Chancellor of Osmania University.
- **Kaushiki Sanyal** is Co-founder and CEO, Sunay Advisory
- **Meera Shenoy** is a pioneer in job-linked skilling of rural, tribal and now youth with disabilities. She was Executive Director, EGMM, the first State government skilling mission, then consulted with the World Bank and UNDP, and is now a Change maker. She set up Youth4Jobs 9 years back which has grown to be the largest organisation in South Asia skilling less educated and educated youth with disabilities and linking them to jobs. Y4J is a one stop shop for 650+ companies has won the highest National and international awards.
- **Tarun** is an IISER Pune alumnus, is a Mathematician by training, who started teaching at 16 and founded Sciensation. Tv at 19, to spreading university-level research-based thinking. Tarun is the founder of DeepThought EduTech Ventures, working towards the ambitious goal of scaling the MIT/Harvard/IISERs kind of education to the rest of the world. DeepThought is replacing the paradigm of “experts teach students” with “senior learners teach junior learners”. They emphasise the mindset/processes over content/curriculum.
- **Umme Salma** is the founding Principal of New York Academy, a progressive American school in Hyderabad. She is also an Adjunct Professor at Notre Dame de Namur University in California. Umme is the Founder and Director of EdPodium, a non-profit organisation in California. EdPodium is committed to building an education ecosystem in India - a Teacher Training Institute, a Lab School and a diversified Professional Learning Community, to help educators learn and practice the Art and Science of learning, teaching and leading.

FACTORS IMPACTING QUALITY OF EDUCATION

Quality in education is affected by a range of factors. While looking at quality in education practices, multiple facets need to be explored. The next section covers those factors that need to be kept in mind while building good quality schools. The section is an amalgamation of excerpts of conversations and experiences shared by some of the biggest changemakers in the field of education as well literature that has been drawn to supplant the prevailing narrative. These experts have been quoted verbatim at places in the document, and at some points, the learnings drawn have been written down inferentially. Having worked in diverse fields within the education sector, each expert advocated how one or several of the following nine aspects can be developed to transform quality in schools. Each of them have talked about strengthening schools using different approaches looking at different perspectives. These nine indicators are arrived at from collating narratives of the experts, however, not all have been discussed by each of them. While these are crucial in developing quality institutions, they must occur in simultaneous waves and one does not accord priority over the other.

I. Education among marginalised groups

The right to education mandates that 25% of students be representative of disadvantaged socio-economic groups. Despite incentives such as Mid-Day Meals and schemes like Samagra Shiksha being in place, the reality is starkly disturbing. As per the National Sample Survey Organisation’s

2017-18 household survey, the number of out-of-school children in India between ages 6-17 years is 3.22 crore, a substantial portion of such children belong to socio-economically disadvantaged groups. Exclusion in classrooms will have long term ramifications on the socio-economic, political and demographic discourse in the country. The enrolments for Muslim students in higher secondary education was at 10% of the total enrolments in 2019-20. The proportion of enrolments declines with an increase in education levels. About 33% of students belonging to Scheduled Castes, Scheduled Tribes and Other Backward Classes drop out of state government schools in Class 10 (Department of School Education and Literacy, 2019-20).

Coleman (1990) affirms that “Educational equality is reached only when the results of schooling (achievement and attitudes) are the same for racial and religious minorities as for the dominant group”.

In India variation in the inputs received at successive levels of education translate into a stark variation in the educational output. There exists a huge contrast between the education received by the privileged class and that received by the marginalised. The well-equipped private schools are located mainly in metropolitan cities offering education services to the privileged, whereas the disadvantaged children are resigned to the fate of inadequate government schools. It is not possible to carry out any meaningful teaching-learning activity owing to the lack of minimum facilities leading to the low learning level of children attending these schools. Children coming from underprivileged backgrounds, most of them first-generation learners, also face difficulties in adjusting to the cultural differences between home and school (Bandyopadhyay, 2006).

Impact

Romana Shaikh believes that marginalisation shows up in classrooms, affects learning and outcomes. Children from difficult circumstances do not receive early childhood education and hence lack basic motor and neuro skills. They have neither seen role models nor have seen education make a difference to those in their community. Research confirms the value of “stable, responsive, nurturing relationships and rich learning experiences in the earliest years that provide lifelong benefits for learning, behavior and both physical and mental health” (Shonkoff and Richmond, 2009)

A World Bank report in May 2018 stated that the income of Indians is more dependent on their parents’ income and educational levels, restricting their chances of rising above the socio-economic strata they are born in (World Bank, 2018). Farhad Merchant is of the opinion that the socio-economically disadvantaged groups are faced with constraints of infrastructure and resources, the dearth of a congenial atmosphere in their homes along with the pressure to perform well. According to him the problem is compounded with the fact that most of these communities do not see education as an investment. Awareness and knowledge that education will help them move up the ladder, this missing awareness results in low aspirations.

Jyotsna Brar highlights that for the low-income groups, education is a luxury. Children from households with nomadic existence often have large gaps in learning. Children living in remote areas barely have access to schools. Prevalence of child labour and segregation of gender-based roles leads to higher drop-out rates among children from underprivileged backgrounds. As per NSSO (2014), about 53% of children between the ages of 5-15 drop out from school in urban areas and 60% of the same group drop out in rural areas. Moreover, parental illiteracy and language barriers add to the woes of children in difficult circumstances. According to the Annual

Status of Education Report (ASER) 2019, one in 10 rural children aged 14-18 years are unable to read a text in their own language meant for children aged 5-7 years. According to Brar, education infrastructure in rural areas is amiss. A huge one-size-fits-all approach makes it almost impossible for a child in a remote village to understand a textbook written in a metropolitan city. Patriarchy also denies girls from receiving meaningful education. As per the NSSO (2014), the gender gap in rural education is as high as 21%. Only 16% of children in Class 1 in 26 surveyed rural districts can read the text at the prescribed level, while almost 40% cannot even recognise letters (ASER, 2019).

What can be done?

Romana Shaikh suggests that learning should be tailored with consideration to the socio-economic environment. Educators must handle such children with more care and love, help the children find belief in themselves. Meeta Sengupta stresses the urgent need to sensitise faculty members on the nuances associated with differently-abled and underprivileged children. Education must become a high-quality process for vulnerable students. Policymakers need to define quality from the lens of the underprivileged as opposed to a rich and bright students' perspective. Enablement's and active supports put in place will reduce the exclusion faced by socio-economically disadvantaged groups. Technology must be specifically leveraged for the poor via specifically designed packages. Merchant believes that education is about mutual respect, collaboration and inclusion. If we are able to understand that each individual learns differently, it will foster an environment that each child is able to learn from the other. Kiran Bir Singh reiterates the point that the education system treats everybody as a collective and that it must change.

'Diversity in schools helps you [students/teachers/administrators] to learn about inclusion, collaboration and working together to achieve creativity, critical thinking and life skills'.
- Farhad Merchant.

Vidyadhan Model

Vidyadhan is a flagship higher education scholarship program endorsed by the Shibulal Family Philanthropic Initiatives. Meritorious students from economically vulnerable backgrounds are provided financial support starting from standard XI till they complete graduation in a degree of their choice. Vidyadhan focuses on the holistic development of youth - preparing them with life skills and employability, thus putting them on track for professional growth.

The scholarship program has 88% of the students coming from financially deprived families, however, in the course of two years, 100% of them were able to bring their families out of poverty. The selection criterion is very meticulous, that includes academic performance, test interview, followed by home visits. The sponsorship program is for a graduate student but starts in Class XI. Besides the financial aspect of the program, there are training programs. Summer camps where students would get together for three or four days and the training would be basically in terms of guidance on life, learning, life and communication skill and career counselling at the graduation stage.

The program looks at students who might drop out after Class 10, intervenes and supports them so that they don't. Those selected will be eligible for two-year scholarship from the Foundation. If they continue to do well, they will be given a scholarship for pursuing any degree course of their interest.

be given a scholarship for pursuing any degree course of their interest. The scholarship amount for graduation courses varies from ₹ 10,000 to ₹ 60,000 per year depending on the state, course, duration etc.

Currently the Vidyadhan program has around 4300 students across the following states: Kerala, Karnataka, Tamil Nadu, Pondicherry, Andhra Pradesh, Gujarat, Maharashtra, Telangana, Goa and Odisha.

With inputs from Pankaj Tripathi

II. Early Childhood Care and Education

Research from disciplines such as neurobiology, economics, and child development has sufficient evidence to prove that the first few years are extremely crucial for life-long development, with most of the brain growth already complete by the time a child is five years old (Haartsen, Jone, & Johnson, 2016). The New Education Policy states that over 85 per cent of a child's brain develops by the age of 6 and stresses providing appropriate care and stimulation of the brain in a child's early years for healthy brain development and growth. The draft NEP 2019 believes the learning crisis occurs even before children enter Std I. Learning crisis occurs either because too many children enter formal schooling before six or too many children enter formal schooling without exposure to ECCE, hence lack readiness for rigours of formal schooling. The ASER 2019 'Early years' survey, indicated that more than 90% of children between ages 4-8 are enrolled in some institution. However, only 50% of students in grade I could perform numeric addition, and 40% could handle numeric subtraction. The survey reported that children's foundational skills improved in each subsequent grade. However, even by Grade III, a substantial percentage of all children were well behind where they were expected to be by the end of Std I (ASER, 2020).

Farhad Merchant highlighted that in the absence of appropriate intervention for early childhood care, children could lose out on crucial years of their lives. He also raises a concern that pre-primary education is not under the purview of a formal system and is largely unregulated. Jyotsna Brar believes that inadequate foundational learning coupled with the vast gap between pre-primary and primary education standards leads to a deterioration in the quality of education.

The Integrated Child Development Services (ICDS) program reaches over 8 million expectant and nursing women. It encompasses 76 million children in 1.26 million Anganwadi centres. ICDS amalgamates healthcare, nutrition and pre-school education into community-based child development centres. However, the program has been more focused on health and nutrition while largely neglecting the pre-school component.

III. Sports

Rekha Dey, a Sports for Development consultant, believes that sports can contribute immensely to inclusive and equitable quality education. By improving retention, it can help improve educational standards. Sports can empower women and girls and build leadership values.

ASER 2018 reported that about 80% of schools had a playground available for students, either inside the school premises or nearby. While 90% of schools in Himachal Pradesh, Haryana, and Maharashtra claimed to have a playground, more than a quarter of schools in Jammu and Kashmir, Bihar, Odisha, and Jharkhand did not have access to a playground. The report also

highlighted a dearth of physical education teachers in rural areas, with only 5.8% of primary schools having a teacher. Only 55.8% of primary schools had some sort of sports equipment (ASER, 2019). According to Dey, In India, sports is only limited to elite schools; low budget or government schools are rarely associated with high engagement levels in sports. The way schools have cropped up in the urban area, the availability of open grounds is certainly a constraint.

Incorporating Sports in School Sports for development has benefited the underprivileged by bringing sports and education together.

Dey feels that sports activities need to be evaluated and monitored to become outcome-driven. While the sector could benefit from investment, volunteer engagement for sports in school could also be explored. Sports must be a regular in the curriculum. The issue of open spaces can be solved by renting municipality grounds. Public-private partnerships and corporate social responsibility can be used to bring in sports facilities comparable to international standards.

Moreover, Dey is of the opinion that equipped sports centres with well-trained coaches could provide avenues for the youth and also employment generation. The relationship between a student and a coach is extremely crucial in streamlining sports into the curriculum. Dey says there are 242 existing jobs in the sports sector, and those need to be popularised to integrate sports at the school level. The myth that the employability of sports is only restricted to professional elite players must also be shattered.

IV. Skill Development

The New Education Policy aims at providing vocational skills to at least 50% of students by 2025 in such a way that the vocational skills acquired at the school level may be further extended up to higher education levels. Given that the educational decisions of youths are often linked to the educational-attainment level of their parents, participation in a vocational track might allow youths from a working-class background to pursue educational attainment beyond the compulsory level, hence their chances of attaining skilled rather than unskilled employment (Shavit and Müller 1998).

Furthermore, with the separation of high- and low-type students, Vocational Education Training (VET) might counteract the equalising potential of vocational education (Shavit and Müller 2000). Given that only a few youths practically manage to enter academic education after vocational schooling, the vocational schooling option is often perceived as a dead-end track and second-choice education in many countries.

However, evidence from the US seems to indicate that, once selection into VET has been accounted for, its participants perform equally or better in terms of employment and wages than high school graduates, and these returns have increased over time. In contrast, evidence in the UK indicates that academic education leads to higher returns. (Kogan 2008, Carrero 2006).

Romana Shaikh believes that skills should provide students with gainful employment when the need arises, but also allow them to resume their academic pursuits as and when they can. According to Meeta Sengupta, spatial awareness that comes from training in carpentry, gardening is also critical for developing values such as leadership and innovation. The idea is to develop hands-on skills, which can be acquired along with academics and not just be restricted to employability.

Incorporating vocational education in curriculum

Sengupta is of the opinion that vocational education must meet expectations and aim for excellence. If vocational education is made mandatory, it should not be done with the idea of lowering expectations on the academic front. Shaikh reinstates that skilling is not a substitute for poor academic performance. In Farhad Merchant's view, VET should be given the same degree of respect as a professional degree. He furthers with the example of German and Chinese trade schools where an apprentice has the same degree of respect as that of a professional degree holder.

German Trade School offer a dual-track program involving classroom-based learning in specialised trade schools as well as on-the-job work experience. Apprentices gain theoretical knowledge at a vocational school along with classes in German, English, and social studies.

Alongside which they also learn practical skills at a company or public sector institution. The trainees usually spend 60 percent of their time in the workplace under the supervision of a certified trainer and 40 percent in the classroom. More than a third of students graduating from secondary school in Germany opt for vocational training programs (Hockenos, 2018).

Vocational education in China is provided at three levels junior secondary, senior secondary and tertiary. Junior vocational education is vocational and technical education after primary school education and is a part of the 9-year compulsory education.

The Junior vocational system is aimed at training workers, peasants and employees in other sectors with basic professional knowledge and certain professional skills. These are mainly located in rural areas where the economy is less developed. Senior secondary schools are to produce secondary-level specialised and technical talents for the forefront of production, and students master the basic knowledge, theory and skills of their speciality in addition to the cultural knowledge required for higher school students. Tertiary schools are aimed at training secondary and high-level specialised technical and management talents needed in economic construction (Ministry of Education of the People's Republic of China, 2006).

V. Assessment and Evaluation

The process of assessment is used to determine the degree to which an individual child possesses a particular ability. The purpose of assessment is to understand a child's overall development. Moreover, it helps a teacher to gauge whether a child is progressing within the academic system. Furthermore, assessment helps to identify children performing poor academically or who need special education services. Academic readiness tests, developmental screening tests, and diagnostic tests are forms of assessments. Evaluation on the other hand is the process of making judgments about the merit, value, or worth of educational programs, projects, materials, or techniques.

Romana Sheikh believes that exams are not helpful either to learners or to the teacher. The purpose of continuous evaluation is to understand progress and that learning is a continuous process. Continuous evaluation provides the idea that learning is about gaining feedback and thus using it to grow. Meeta Sengupta says that the assessment and evaluation in education should measure how much one has progressed from where one was. Tarun opines that the focus

should be on allowing insight-based competition rather than trivia-based. Merchant feels that poor evaluation can increase learning gaps.

Jyotsna Brar says the language is a major barrier – parents, children and even teachers in several parts of the country have no familiarity with English and hence resort to rote learnings. In education, marks are regarded as the end-point and no one is actually assessing whether or not real learning is happening.

Gowri Iswaran reaffirms that academic performance is the end-all of the education system. Textbooks are looked on as the master, but they are only tools. The potential of each human being should not be confined simply to their grade card. Children should be allowed to find their own paths, and the education system must help them achieve those goals. Success should not be benchmarked by grades.

VI. Values in education

Schools play a crucial role in building and evolving the values children have already begun to develop by further introducing them to the values present in the society, such as equality and respect for diversity; and to help children to reflect, understand and apply values on their own (Halstead and Taylor, 2000).

Modernisation, economic and technological developments have resulted in intense competition among nations. Values of entrepreneurship, competitiveness and individualism have assumed precedence over social cohesion and cooperation. Schools, too, have focused their energies to help individuals thrive in competition. Thereby, neglecting values such as friendship, respect, and cooperation that contribute to peace and fraternity (Gökçe, 2021). Umme Salma says, “Education must focus on improvement of students, see effort as a way to build their abilities and failure as a natural part of the learning process”.

Gowri Iswaran states that schools have the challenge to prepare children for jobs that have not yet been created, technology that has not been invented and problems that have not yet arisen. She also reaffirms the need to imbibe humanity in children by sensitising them to moral values and extending and developing the ability to face risks and uncertainty and follow one’s passion. Schools that marry competence and humanity will be able to produce fuller human beings. So far most schools have done a poor job of inculcating 21st-century skills such as innovation, collaboration and team spirit.

Iswaran believes that collaboration and teamwork, which are relatively easy to inculcate, have a whole bunch of side benefits. They allow the growth of other values such as integrity, trust and respect for others.

Moreover, whether or not the students and teachers feel comfortable and enjoy their time at school is equally important. Classrooms that are airy and have greenery around them help build student happiness. Furthermore, instilling gratitude in students will enable them to be good citizens willing to take responsibility.

According to Kiran Bir, schools reward students as long as they listen or repeat what is dictated by the authority. This learning experience creates citizens devoid of confidence and resigned to a fate of passivity and status quoists. Fear and passivity ingrained in young minds make learning less likely. Education must move from a space of fear or frustration to a space of optimism and

creativity. The idea is to listen to the children rather than tell them. Looking at children with filters of age, gender, and other such demographic classifications diminish their potential. She suggests the use of design thinking in education to completely remove these filters to allow the creation of a humane framework and an I Can Mindset.

Singh believes that for values to be actionable, value education must be consistently routine in school timetables. A student must graduate with content and character. We treat all students like a collective and it must all go.

Schools need a coherent strategy for encouraging values in education. Empirical studies show bringing together a variety of teaching and learning approaches is much more effective in impacting the development of young people's values than adopting a single approach in isolation. There is a need to understand values development and methods of values education that needed to be imparted at the teacher training level (Halstead and Taylor, 2000).

Shaikh highlights that the goal of education is to allow learners to enquire into who they are. Tarun believes 'the higher aims of education involve looking at the inner potential of the learner and the lower aims are seeing education as means of livelihood generation. Utilitarian perspectives of learning are myopic'. The goal of education is to be a value-based mission. Education must create future leaders with a belief in culture, says Farhad Merchant.

Design thinking in Education

In order to find solutions to a problem, the idea is to engage with the people who are affected and afflicted and then craft a solution. The idea is to slow down and look at possibilities, find possibilities with the user. Whether it is looking at assessment or the spaces, it should not be done without the user. Design thinking is about reframing the user experience, understanding it and then activating the solution. Every stakeholder becomes a parent and incidental to the whole learning program. Localised solutions depend on what needs to be focussed on to improve the quality of education. Design thinking should engage students and allow them to explore different tools to create pragmatic and creative solutions to solve difficult problems and satisfy human wants. Moreover, design thinking can help develop teacher professionalism (Koh et. al, 2015).

With inputs from Kiran Bir Singh

VII. Technology in Education

Technology has immensely redefined education. Gowri Iswaran confirms that, with the advent of smartphones and the internet, the teacher is no longer the only person who gives out information to their students. The use of technology may very well give out more information, yet it by itself, cannot assure how that information is to be verified or used. This is now the job of the teacher. Technology has bridged the gap between teachers and students. A few teachers can reach a massive student population.

Jyotsna Brar highlights the huge digital divide in education. She feels that without proper training and infrastructure, the boon of technology cannot be utilised. While tech platforms can be used for teaching and professional learning, a vast majority of children do not have access to mobile devices.

Ritesh Singh, CEO , Eckovation also opines that a tech platform can greatly enhance the quality of educators. However, any technology solution deployed in education must have extensive reach. Apps that reach one-to-many, gauge responses to quizzes, understand the learning curve and give feedback can be transmitted to underserved areas. While may compromise with retaining students, but can ensure better inclusion. Moreover, digitising these responses can help to develop a learning curve.

However, the integration of technology needs an understanding of the entire psychology of the partners and the stakeholders. Headmasters, parents and students need to be on board. The whole model places teachers at the centre for content development and disbursement, which ensures sustainability. The program must be owned by the local stakeholders. So teachers, students and parents are involved very closely with the model. For unreachable areas in Bihar, Assam and Rajasthan, the contextualised content for these districts is available to be telecasted on Doordarshan, while it does not ensure individual attention, it at least allows for learning to happen in difficult circumstances.

Technology needs to be innovated to challenges in different regions. Mobile vans going into underserved regions, with teachers teaching students and then returning. Technology needs social reformation, understanding of stakeholders and end-users. End-users who may not be high on digital literacy, do not own laptops and need a simplified version of the technology. Ritesh believes that if the tech solution is confined to mobiles, we may never come out of the digital divide. The solution should be defined or designed in a way where it facilitates one-to-many models of consumption of education.

Digital education can improve retention rates as well as provide standardised quality in education in the absence of quality teaching. Moreover, it allows to be teachers to be moderators while delivering a vast variety of content.

VIII. Parents

Kiran Bir believes that the education system in many ways serves parents rather than being an agent of change for children. Schools that have been extremely engaged with parents have their own pains, and schools that have been reluctant to engage with them have also seen their own set of challenges. A parent body is a team that is genuinely appreciative and wants to make a difference, the school and parent body team learn to respect the decisions. A group of parents who love their children a lot, understand the why's, are happy to follow through with the what and how. The engagement between the parent body and school needs to be codified to develop a sense of trust and respect. A rational model rather than a defensive mechanism with parental cooperation for initiatives created will help sustain the chain of process.

IX. Teacher Training

Pankaj Jain describes what makes a good school - a good team of teachers, headed by a principal and has sound infrastructure. A good school combines the three elements in good measure.

Jain believes that policies ensure that teachers come with basic education and preparation of the mind. Certain necessary capabilities are mandated by policies and have been updated from time to time. The focus has been on teacher education and how to develop a good teacher education. Teacher qualification has been significantly high in India.

He goes on to explain that teacher incentives are seen in multiples of per capita income. OECD countries, on average, pay their teachers 1.2-1.8 times their respective per capita income. Developing countries such as Indonesia pay an average of 3-4 times their per capita income. India pays an average of about 7-8 times its per capita income. Thus, India meets both qualification and incentives criteria.

Spending on Education

The OECD report on education claims that they spend 5-6% on education, including private and government spending. However, spending by society on education is one of the highest in India. (Both household and Government).

Jain goes on to list the problems that lie in the model of school we have tried to adopt/ implement.

He says we have relied on the formal education of teachers as the major input of a teacher's competency; however, much of the education takes place in the workforce. Teacher capacity cannot be developed with education. Degrees do not produce a better teacher.

He believes that the education system expects that teachers should hold fort in different subjects. The school system needs to mentor and supervise teachers for growth; the present school have small teams hence not conducive for the growth of teachers in the long run. The system is not designed for good teacher capability, despite incentives or teacher qualification.

Pankaj Jain is of the opinion that we will continue to have poor schooling performance unless the model changes. Furthermore, the traditional model of improving teacher capacity has been saturated – in-service training, pre-service norms and incentives will not produce remarkable results. A child will learn with even modest support and teacher quality.

He also feels that the curriculum design should be centred around the things that a child is being made to do in class alone or with peers. How is each activity of the child being planned and assigned, what will a child listen to and what task he/she can perform alone or in partnership?

Pankaj Jain explains how the cost per child can be brought down-

The cost per child can be brought down with a modest-quality teacher and paying modest salaries. About 85% is the cost allotted to teachers. We do not need expensive teachers.

Further, he describes the abilities to be looked at while recruiting teachers:

- Cognitive capability
- How does the teacher relate to the child?
- The system must be pleasant to the teacher.

He suggests training high school students to become teachers. The teacher training curriculum has limited functionality; the useful part is limited and can be covered in less time. Following this approach can drastically cut down on teacher training costs.

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WHAT MAKES A GOOD SCHOOL?

This section take a case study approach to understand the journey's undertaken by different schools in a bid to bring quality to education practices. The team had come up with an exhaustive list of schools covering diverse curriculums, mediums, managements among other markers. However, the outbreak of the pandemic and the closure of schools as well as difficulties faced by the schools during these times were a major impediment in covering all those schools in the list. Hence, the schools listed below are the ones that allowed CDPP to conduct this research and were open about their practice.

AL FALAH SCHOOL

Year of Establishment	2011
Name of the Trust / Society	Al Falah Educational Trust
Founder	Fouzia Khan
Teacher / Student Ratio	1:25
No. of Students	1200
Board	CBSE
Medium of Instruction	English
Minority / Non-Minority	Non-Minority
Private / Govt.	Private
Boys / Girls / Co-ed	Co-education

HISTORY / EVOLUTION: EARLY DAYS, GROWTH PHASE, PRESENT STATUS:

Al Falah School was founded in June 2011 by Dr. Fouzia Khan, an educator at the core. She picked up five orphan children from the street with the intent to make them educated and successful. The school undoubtedly reflects her farsighted vision for the cause of education. She believes in inclusive education as the key to human enrichment and India's giant strides to progress. Al Falah has state of the art facilities and infrastructure to support her vision and endeavour to make education a holistic and pleasant experience. The hostel at Al Falah is accommodated with a hundred orphan kids, both boys and girls. The student strength at Al Falah (2021-2022) is 1200 students. It is recognised by the Central Board of Secondary Education (CBSE). The school lays a strong foundation for character building and academic excellence among students so that they deal with the challenges of the future.

The school's mission is to prepare each student for academic, social and personal growth by creating a community of empowered and diverse learners, striving to be cosmopolitan citizens in an atmosphere of mutual respect, understanding and trust. The administration, staff, and students are committed to this mission and work together to obtain exceptional academic, co-curricular and extracurricular results at this day-boarding cum residential School.

Al Falah School has an idyllic setting, a sprawling campus amidst hills and fields, favourable weather, and a pollution-free atmosphere. The students are able to learn, observe, introspect and evolve in a serene atmosphere. Education in such an ambience is a rewarding experience for their students. Al Falah aims to provide a solid foundation by developing the child intellectually as well as socially,

morally, physically and emotionally by providing a stimulating, nurturing and relaxed environment. Al Falah attempts to bridge the gap between the comfortable environs of a child's home and the rigours of formal education. Their passion is to turn education into a beautiful voyage of discovery.

They have some unique programs in place. Their emphasis is on equipping students with knowledge of basics. Moreover, they have an English language drive where students systematically develop their vocabulary and learn new words with great ease. Another novel feature at Al Falah is teaching life skills and moral science concepts together with academic concepts. They have a 'perfect tarbiyat (teaching etiquette and manners) program' to help their students improve life skills.

Most of their teachers are first-aid trained and regularly attend professional development workshops. The teaching methods and interactive classrooms are vital elements in creating a healthy and safe environment. They have a strict policy on discipline and separate blocks for boys and girls. Al Falah boasts of a well-endowed library, an equipped pre-primary section and a science lab, a range of sports activities with indoor and outdoor facilities. Although a rigorous academic program is at the core of everything, the school has an equally outstanding co-curricular and extracurricular agenda for students that provides much-needed holistic education.

Learnings

If given the education ecosystem at par with regular students, children from underprivileged roots can achieve similar outcomes in learning. An emphasis on strengthening fundamentals is often lost in the rat race to achieve perfect scores. However, Al Falah's attempt to empower students with basics is noteworthy. Their special program to develop values along with academic excellence is of particular significance given the falling standards of morals and ethics.

AZAAAN INTERNATIONAL SCHOOL

Year of Establishment	2006
Name of the Trust / Society	Anwarunnissa Charitable Trust
Founder	Chairman - Mohammed Yousuf Azam
Student / Teacher Ratio	1:14
No. of Students	800+
Board	Central Board of Secondary Education (CBSE)
Medium of Instruction	English
Minority / Non-Minority	Minority Institution
Private / Govt.	Private
Boys / Girls / Co-ed	Boys and Girls Study in the same campus with segregated classes

HISTORY/EVOLUTION: EARLY DAYS, GROWTH PHASE, PRESENT STATUS:

The school was started with a vision to provide education together with values to help students become productive citizens of the society. Many schools that offer good education often miss out on producing a fuller and more well-rounded human being. At AIS, both these aspects are well-integrated within the schooling system. The school has registered impressive growth and owes its spectacular success to the able leadership, diligent governance, the experience of its governing board and the unflinching support from the parents. The focus on value-based education, regular meetings and training opportunities enable teachers to become role models and lead by example. The management undertakes regular supervision to ensure that the assimilation of values happens along with the curriculum. The focus is to help hone the innate talents of students along with their spiritual and moral quotient. The end goal is to groom a spiritually & intellectually superior future generation. The school's efforts have been recognised and awarded by various renowned agencies like British Council – ISA and the Education Asia group for Innovation in Education.

Learnings

The emphasis on moral values has been consistent at Azaan International; constant efforts have been undertaken to ensure that spiritual and moral growth happen alongside academics. Teachers are supported with subject-specific workshops, value-based workshops and teaching. All Teachers are encouraged to use teaching aids and make the classes interesting. Live classes held during the pandemic were interactive to ensure students retain their interest in the online mode of learning. School had cut down fees, provided 100% fee discount for orphans and several scholarships to deserving students to help ease the burden of the parents during the pandemic. A particularly important takeaway is that despite the lack of an adequately sized ground, the student's physical development is taken care of with the support of physical education experts from Edusports. Apart from daily physical routines, the facilities offer sports enthusiasts expert coaching in various disciplines.

A contentious issue revealed by AIS was their relationship with the student's parents. The school has a tough time dealing with the casual attitude of parents with regards to payment of fees and responsibilities towards the school. The parent community does not regard education as an investment.

CHOWRAHA JINSI GOVT. PRIMARY SCHOOL

Year of Establishment	-
Name of the Trust / Society	-
Founder	-
Student / Teacher Ratio	1:25
No. of Students	170
Board	SSC
Medium of Instruction	Urdu
Minority / Non-Minority	Non-Minority
Private / Govt.	Govt.
Boys / Girls / Co-ed	Co-ed

HISTORY/EVOLUTION: EARLY DAYS, GROWTH PHASE, PRESENT STATUS:

This Chowraha Jinsi Govt. Primary School is a typical Govt. school in Hakeempet, Hyderabad, without proper infrastructure. There was no boundary wall or a gate. The school would house rag-pickers and hooligans in the evening until the teachers and students came to school the following day.

The absence of toilets or clean drinking water kept even the most eager students stay away. The floors used to be cleaned by students who made it to school and their teachers. Mid-day meals were probably the reason these poor students attended school despite all odds.

Access Foundation – a local NGO took the initiative to work with the school and meet the parents of the 150 enrolled students. Access collaborated with an MNC Cognizant Technology Solutions to conduct a clothing and blanket distribution drive, which attracted several parents. Parents were received by about 20 counsellors to understand the mindset and figure out reasons apart from the obvious ones and address them.

The lack of toilets was one of the primary reasons why students, especially girls, stayed away from attending school. These parents preferred that their children work in small scale industries and earn wages rather than attending school. The NGO coordinated with the local MLA and Govt. body to provide basic facilities in the school. The partnership with Cognizant’s Outreach – CSR put the school back in shape. Hard and consistent work from Cognizant volunteers each week, NGOs support and hard-working teachers could bring an unbelievable change in the school.

The Government, the local MLA, the GHMC Counsellor, Cognizant and Access Foundation transformed the primary school, and the building could even host the high school classes/students, which would earlier run in a rented space in the nearby area.

Learnings

Facilities such as clean toilet, potable drinking water, decent classroom structures can go a long way in improving enrolment and retention rates. Chowraha Jinsi is a prime example of how a school’s partnership with civil society and CSR networks can transform the existing infrastructure into a conducive learning environment. The school is also a fine example of how placing children and mothers at the centre of policy interventions increases enrollments and participation.

CREEKSIDE INTERNATIONAL SCHOOL

Year of Establishment	2010
Name of the Trust / Society	Qamar Education Society
Founder	Chairman - Mohammed Misbahuddin
Student / Teacher Ratio	1:11
No. of Students	500
Board	CBSE
Medium of Instruction	English
Minority / Non-Minority	Minority
Private / Govt.	Private
Boys / Girls / Co-ed	Co-ed

HISTORY/EVOLUTION: EARLY DAYS, GROWTH PHASE, PRESENT STATUS:

The school is situated in the outskirts of the city with an ample space and infrastructure. The school was set up with the intention of catering to both academic and life skills. The founder set up the school to impart quality education along with Quranic and Arabic education. The founder's vision was to produce balanced human beings. The school started with 6 students in 2010 and presently has 500 students studying in it. Many skill development programmes are introduced in the school to develop life skills among students. It is a centre of excellence for value-based education.

Creekside International School is spread across a lush and green 3.5-acre campus. The classrooms are bright and airy with a good teacher-student ratio. The school has indoor and outdoor games, a well-equipped lab and audio-visual rooms.

There is a particular focus on weak students to streamline the slow learners. Special classes are conducted for such students. The primary teachers are provided assistant teachers with the purpose of giving individual attention to each student. The students are taken for the field trips twice a year. Students attend Olympiads and have won at the state level. The school has had 100% results so far. Special fee concessions are given to the students from financially challenged backgrounds.

Learnings

The school uses skilling classes to build confidence and promote all-round development of students. Parents need to be counselled for them to see education as an investment.

FOCUS HIGH SCHOOL

Year of Establishment	2013
Name of the Trust / Society	Jafaria Institute of Social Medicine
Founder	Minhaj Arastu
Student / Teacher Ratio	1:16
No. of Students	1200
Board	IB / SSC
Medium of Instruction	English
Minority / Non-Minority	Non-Minority
Private / Govt.	Private
Boys / Girls / Co-ed	Co-ed

HISTORY/EVOLUTION: EARLY DAYS, GROWTH PHASE, PRESENT STATUS:

Focus was founded by a group of philanthropic businessmen and professionals who wanted to provide access to high quality, holistic education in the Old City of Hyderabad in 2013. The founder of the school is Minhaj Arastu. It is under Jafaria Institute of Social Medicine (JISM) which is the registered society that works in the health and education. Focus has two campuses, with primary classes at Noor Khan Bazar and secondary classes at Darushifa. The infrastructure is designed for safety, supporting effective teaching and learning.

The school has built a conducive learning environment based on understanding and respect. They have an open house every week. Focus is a community that engages all stakeholders in the pursuit of knowledge. Focus students do not simply consume knowledge produced by others; instead, they create understanding and develop inquiry, reflection, self-management, collaboration, and listening skills. Students are expected to be committed participants in society. In fact, guests who interact with focus students are impressed with the questions and energy of the children.

Teachers at Focus are the campaigners of life-long learning for students. Each year the school organises and takes part in numerous seminars for professional development. Teachers are encouraged and supported to pursue courses and conferences that will help them to inspire children. The faculty boasts of a CENTA certified teacher, an all-India topper in the Teaching Professionals Olympiad, and dozens of teachers pursuing further education and certifications. An internship program is the centrepiece of their learning community, through which they induct new members into the teaching profession with the guidance and support of lead teachers.

Focus does not limit itself to textbooks and examinations alone; instead, it strives for the holistic development of children within the framework of the International Baccalaureate Primary Years Programme and the Telangana State secondary curriculum. Focus High School is the only IB authorised school in the Old City, a significant accomplishment given IB's demanding standards.

The teachers at Focus tirelessly work to stoke curiosity in children's minds and put together thought-provoking experiences. The school nurtures and challenges the high achieving students by encouraging them to participate in various interschool events. Focus seeks to widen access to IB programmes in several ways. Thus, the fee structure is such that common people can afford the costs. The school provides for students' holistic development - encouraging students to be critical and creative thinkers; guiding them to be principled and compassionate; training them for physical health; and preparing them for higher studies and employment. Convinced that education is a means of establishing justice and mercy in the world, Focus High School ensures that its programmes are accessible to all.

Learnings

Each members of the Focus community seeks to improve, learn, and grow. Focus strives for the integrated development of children's intellectual, emotional, social, spiritual, and physical aspects of life. According to Focus, learning is a process of "constructing, testing and revising mental models of how the world works, and it is this process that enables each student to make meaning of their lives and the world around them". The school serves male & female children of varied communities, economic backgrounds, and academic abilities, this diversity allows for the growth of mutual tolerance and respect. Leadership in the school is distributed and devolved, relying on the active collaboration of creative and reflective teachers. The school is conscientiously trying to support each student as per their needs. Focus High School is the only IB authorised school in the Old City, a significant accomplishment given IB's demanding standards. Focus, like many other schools, also faces problems with parental cooperation.

GLENDALE INTERNATIONAL SCHOOL

Year of Establishment	2003
Name of the Trust / Society	Hyderabad Educational Academy
Founder	Basheer Uddin Babukhan
Student / Teacher Ratio	1:20
No. of Students	3000
Board	CBSE / IB
Medium of Instruction	English
Minority / Non-Minority	Non-minority
Private / Govt.	Private
Boys / Girls / Co-ed	Co-ed

HISTORY/EVOLUTION: EARLY DAYS, GROWTH PHASE, PRESENT STATUS:

Glendale Academy was envisioned by Basheer Uddin Babukhan, who was already running a chain of schools called Springfields. A well-known politician and a philanthropist, he established an unconventional school called Glendale Academy in 2003.

Anjum Babukhan, the school director, intended to create lifelong learners, having a twin focus on building academic competence and character. She found the educational system in India outdated, rigid and incompetent for the same.

Glendale offers an environment that exposes young minds to mental stimulation and physical strength. The expansive playground with a petting zoo provides students with opportunities to explore a variety of sports, develop team and competitive spirit, and learn compassion.

Empathy and inclusiveness are crucial to the pedagogy at Glendale Academy. Their belief is that 'The more ways they teach, the more children they reach'. The school also aims to develop desirable traits such as responsibility, generosity and compassion through innovative learning methods.

The RRC- Respect, Responsibility and Cooperation culture along with the integration of United Nations Sustainable Development goals and the concept of the 'Leader in Me' has helped to sow the seeds of character in young minds. Dr. Howard Gardner's Multiple Intelligence methodology, Eric Jensen's Brain-Compatible Learning Strategies and the Cs of the 21st century are some critical elements used while devising learning strategies.

The teachers at Glendale undergo a rigorous professional development program at regular intervals. This program aims to make the teachers acquainted with practical and innovative teaching trends.

Learnings

The school curriculum is innovative and scientifically designed. Multiple Intelligence is integrated into their curriculum to develop the innate potential of each child. The school believes that "the more ways they teach, the more children they reach. Glendale has a unique philosophy of internationally researched methodologies that integrates academics, personality development and universal human values for the holistic growth of their students.

HYDERABAD PUBLIC SCHOOL

Year of Establishment	1972
Name of the Trust / Society	Hyderabad Public School Society
Founder	Seventh Nizam of Hyderabad – Mir Osman Ali Khan
Student / Teacher Ratio	1:23
No. of Students	2300
Board	CBSE
Medium of Instruction	English
Minority / Non-Minority	Non-Minority
Private / Govt.	Private
Boys / Girls / Co-ed	Co-ed

HISTORY/EVOLUTION: EARLY DAYS, GROWTH PHASE, PRESENT STATUS:

HPS Begumpet was established by Mir Osman Ali Khan in the year 1923. After a period of fifty years, in the year 1972, another branch of Hyderabad Public School was established in Ramanthapur, Hyderabad, on 40 acres of land. The school is managed by The Hyderabad Public School Society through its Board of Governors. It has over 2300 students from pre-primary through 12th. The teacher-student ratio is 1:23 and the school is affiliated with the Central Board of Secondary Education. The school is an ethical, non-profitable, co-educational institution.

Hyderabad Public School aims to provide holistic education, where each child is a valued partner. The child is facilitated to achieve his or her optimum potential to meet the challenges of life, enabling him or her to be a global citizen and future leader. The mission of HPS is to improve the students' communication skills, instil a sense of respect for others and the environment while being appreciative of individual differences at the same time. They prepare the students for life and aim at inculcating value-based education that nurtures the young learners inside and out. HPS Ramanthapur has been ranked number 3 in Telangana and Number 12 in the country by education world. HPS believes in incorporating technology and innovation in education.

When learners readily adopt and adapt technology, the learning experience is transformed. At HPS, the aim is to build a holistic learning environment that plays a significant role in the cognitive development of the students. The school has established collaborative practices in which teachers and students are co-learners. The school has tried to shift away from traditional delivery towards a more student-centric and constructive model, project-based learning in which the teacher is a guide. The focus is increasingly on participation and deliberation rather than direction and instruction. The school believes in the democratisation of education, an approach in education that is done with and by learners rather than done to them. The institutions aims to build capacity through interdependence.

HPS stresses the necessity to incorporate life skills along with reading, writing and arithmetic - communication skills, goal setting, decision-making, conflict resolution, interpersonal and critical thinking are imparted. The school also focuses immensely on peer-group interaction and the learnings that are gained through group activities. The skills that the students learn in such engagements greatly enhance their academic performance and help them interact better with friends, family members and eventually at their workplaces.

To motivate this generation to be leaders of tomorrow, HPS is committed to developing leadership skills that allow children to think big, speak their minds, take the initiative, analyse information, and manage time and money, thereby making them successful learners and active citizens.

Learnings

HPS has students from diverse backgrounds, allowing children to learn and overcome differences. HPS has gained the 'Highest Happiness Quotient' with parents. Professional development via training sessions for teachers is encouraged. HPS follows the flip-board method that helps impart innovative ideas and practical learning. HPS believes in instilling leadership as the end goal of school education. They often use the power of their stellar alumni to conduct engaging sessions for their students.

IQRA MISSION HIGH SCHOOL

Year of Establishment	1986
Name of the Trust / Society	Iqra Education Society
Founder	Mohammed Sajid Ali
Student / Teacher Ratio	1:25
No. of students	1800+
Board	Secondary School Certificate (S.S.C.) Telengana State Board
Medium of Instruction	English
Minority / Non-Minority	Minority Institution
Private / Govt.	Budget Private School
Boys / Girls / Co-ed	Co-Edu

HISTORY/EVOLUTION: EARLY DAYS, GROWTH PHASE, PRESENT STATUS:

In the early days of its establishment, the focus was on the school's growth and making it acceptable to the demands of a neighbourhood living below the poverty. The school managed to gain ground through various tedious yet successful efforts to create trust and a zeal for learning.

The school adopted several measures to ensure quality education at an affordable price. The emphasis was on making a generation literate to ensure upward mobility of the community. Steadily the school inched towards its vision and churned successful students year after year. A special coaching program after school, an overhaul of school policies to suit the stakeholders' expectations, counselling and dialogue with the parent community to help support learners through home interventions are a part of the success story of this school.

Owing to the pandemic the school has faced drawbacks in the learners' attitudes and school finances. The school's finances have been stretched to hire and retain staff that can deliver better teaching and learning experiences. The school is facing financial pressure as it serves low-income groups with an affordable fee structure and is finding it difficult to hire good teachers who demand higher salaries.

Learnings

Visionary leadership of the school correspondent has helped contribute in raising awareness and educating students belonging to the underprivileged community (daily wage workers). Good quality education at a reasonable cost. Teachers are well supported with a series of in-house training programmes to adopt novel teaching techniques. Senior faculty often model the best practices during the staff development sessions.

The school staff has filmed concept videos to enable students to access the lessons conveniently through their website. This has benefitted the enrolled students and those students who have missed schooling due to the pandemic. The school charges fees for ten months from students and has one of the most economical fee structures amongst budget private schools in the old city area. The students get a wide range of exposure through meaningful field trips to places around Hyderabad, ensuring exposure and newer perspectives.

MADINA PUBLIC SCHOOL

Year of Establishment	1980
Name of the Trust / Society	The Madina Education and Welfare Society
Founder	K.M. Arifuddin
Student / Teacher Ratio	1:15
No. of Students	1800
Board	CBSE
Medium of Instruction	English
Minority / Non-minority	Minority
Private / Govt.	Private
Boys / Girls / Co-ed	Co-edu

HISTORY/EVOLUTION: EARLY DAYS, GROWTH PHASE, PRESENT STATUS:

The school is situated in the heart of the city. Started in the year 1982, the school has played a pivotal role in raising the standards of education for Muslim minorities in particular and all other communities in general. From a humble beginning, Madina has made tremendous strides over the years under the inspiration of one selfless and dedicated visionary. The enormous response and demand for good education in the twin cities led to the origin of Madina Public School.

Islamic values and ethics are an integral part of the school and in accordance with the parents' wishes. Madina's emphasis is not simply on literacy but on meaningful education, catering to the challenges of the present society.. The school is now at par with missionaries and corporate schools in the twin cities and has achieved 100% results for the last 36 years.

The school has both the parent and student counsellors for guidance and support. Madina successfully transformed itself from SSC to CBSE syllabus. The mission of the school is to establish a centre of innovative learning where teachers collaborate with students in developing pedagogical applications.

The students are given the opportunity to use the latest technology in education to develop problem-solving and critical thinking skills across the curriculum. Co-curricular activities are given equal importance, all the students need to participate in activities held in the school.

Apart from academics, the school believes in instilling civic sense and social responsibility. Regular teacher training programs are organised for the teachers as a continuous process. Mini-workshops for the students are organised to help them build concentration, memory and learning skills.

Learnings

The students are given the opportunity to use the latest technology to develop problem solving and critical thinking skills across the curriculum. The co-curricular activities are given equal importance, all the students need to participate in activities held in the school. The attempt to inculcate civic sense and social responsibility is particularly significant. Training program for teachers and workshops for students is a remarkable idea to keep the process of learning continuous.

MOUNT MERCY SCHOOL

Year of Establishment	1999
Name of the Trust / Society	Al-Asr Educational Society
Founders	Indian Professionals working in Saudi Arabia
Student / Teacher Ratio	1:17
No. of students	800
Board	SSC
Medium of Instruction	English
Minority / Non-Minority	Non-minority
Private/Govt.	Private
Boys/Girls/Co-ed	Co-ed

HISTORY/EVOLUTION: EARLY DAYS, GROWTH PHASE, PRESENT STATUS:

After lengthy deliberations, a group of Indian professionals working in Saudi Arabia concluded that the emancipation of the Muslim community lies in education. The other major conclusion was that there is a need to provide quality education at an affordable cost, and the discussion yielded shape in the form of Mount Mercy School which was inaugurated in the year 1999.

The school management believes in equality, respect for all faiths and creeds and social justice. The aim of the school is to develop a responsible attitude among children to make them independent.

At Mount Mercy, a combination of approaches are used to give the best learning experience to the students. While academics are given their due importance, attention is also accorded to nurturing various talents among children.

MMS is a co-educational Institute from pre-primary to 10th. It follows the state syllabus and is recognised by the government of Andhra Pradesh. Moreover, has been achieving excellent results in the SSC examination. It is housed in a three-storey structure with lively interiors. An open space of 1000 sq. m in front of the building is used as a playground.

The school has always given due attention to technology and introduced digi-learning or smart learning in 2013. Each floor is equipped with a smartboard used for students from UKG to 10th. This new audio-visual aid has brought about a major change in teaching. The students have taken up to digi-learning enthusiastically.

The principal plays an essential role in improving the quality of the school. The school's strength is 800 students, and the teacher-student ratio is 1:17. The principal takes up home visits to find out the issues faced by the slow learners. Regular counselling sessions for children, parents and families are held to help them identify shortcomings and overcome them. They believe that if a child is happy at heart, he is an achiever; hence, a significant focus is on making a child 'happy' rather than on marks. The house visits by the principal and teachers did help in improving the standards of the child's performance.

Empathy is a trait instilled among students at MMS through prayers, Joy of Giving, Joy of sharing and special assemblies. The school successfully collected the amount of rupees 2.5 lacs from the students for a school child who was sick and needed money for his treatment. Foodgrains and money are collected from the students for the deserving people. A few financially underprivileged students are given meals in school. MMS believes in providing opportunities to all regardless of income - 400 students were allowed to take online classes despite not paying the fees.

The school has an open house every Saturday, where the talents and achievements of students are showcased. The children have demonstrated a praiseworthy performance in academics, oration, essay writing, arts, dramatics, music and sports. A remarkable surge in their confidence levels and self-esteem was seen after the children started participating in various contests and inter-school competitions. A school development plan exists and more than a majority of the plan is followed.

Multiple teacher training programs are organised, and regular assessment of the teachers is one of the many practices adopted to maintain the standard of the teaching staff. The principal herself meets with the staff every Saturday after the open house where various issues and their solutions are discussed. Peer teaching and training is encouraged at MMS. The school is equipped with science and math labs, a library, digital classes and proper sports facilities. Both curricular and co-curricular activities are given equal importance. The school imparts martial arts and defence training for both girls and boys.

MMS had 26 specially-abled children in the school, and a trained teacher was appointed to help them. These students were placed according to their age in the classes and a substantial change was noticed in the growth and development of these children when they were placed with the regular kids.

For Mount Mercy School, education means leading a healthy and happy life, and the school champions this cause in their everyday practice.

Learnings

For a child to be successful, he/she must be happy at heart. The school believes that a child's happiness at home and school, is an important determinant for his/her success. The home visits by the principal herself, is a noteworthy intervention and helps in understanding a child's overall well-being. It is remarkable how the school has integrated specially-abled children in regular classrooms. In this world driven by competition and hunger for success, the school tries to inculcate the value of empathy among the students through carefully crafted activities. Multiple teacher training programs are organised and regular assessment of the teachers is one of the many practices adopted to maintain the standard for the teaching staff.

PRINCESS ESIN GIRLS' HIGH SCHOOL

Year of Establishment	In 1971, a lab school was established for students seeking a Diploma in Pre-School education, became a full-fledged school in 2001
Name of the Trust / Society	Nizamia Hyderabad Women's Association Trust
Founder	Prince Mufakkham Jah and Princess Esin
Student / Teacher Ratio	1:25
No. of Students	2700 Approximately
Board	CISCE (Council for Indian School Certificate Examination)
Medium of Instruction	English
Minority / Non-Minority	Minority
Private / Govt.	Private
Boys / Girls / Co-ed	Girls' School

HISTORY/EVOLUTION: EARLY DAYS, GROWTH PHASE, PRESENT STATUS:

Princess Esin's Girls' High School was founded almost 40 years ago. At that time, the general populace was conservative and reluctant to educate women. They wanted to marry their girls at a young age, given that there were not many safe and secure educational centres. It was a difficult decision for most parents to send their daughters to study at prominent educational institutes which were located far from the old city area. The visionary founders, concerned with illiteracy in the community, started the Nizamia Hyderabad Women's Association Trust.

The trust started a vocational centre that provided a teaching diploma to the local girls. The girls could then take up teaching positions in the city schools, a vocation acceptable amongst the under-privileged conservative families of the old city. The institution attempted to raise the academic and economic standards of the community.

The school is located in the heritage buildings belonging to the family of the last Nizam of Hyderabad. The descendants of the royal family sought to use the building for the purpose of providing affordable and good quality schools for girls. After the 'Teachers Training Institute', a 'Lab School' was started which admitted students from the neighbouring areas. With classes being added each year the strength has now reached approximately 2700 students. The school has added an extension block to accommodate its students.

Learnings

The curriculum has a blend of coursework and vocational subjects like cooking and (Socially Useful Productive work) SUPW work which equips young students with skills for life. A dedicated team of teachers has served in this institution for two decades. Some alumni of this institution also serve as teachers. Teachers are regularly trained to help them keep abreast with the latest teaching concepts. Teachers are suitably paid and enjoy benefits related to continued service, which ensures job satisfaction. High school students receive need-based and merit-based scholarships as an incentive to complete their school education. All orphans receive a 100% scholarship. Steady and robust leadership has helped transform education for girls in the Old City of Hyderabad.

Challenges faced by these schools

- In most schools, the attitude of parents is an enabling factor in providing quality education. Most schools highlighted that parent does not see education as an investment, which in turn impacts fee collection and subsequently budgetary allocations.
- Despite teacher training programs, improving teaching quality has been a major hurdle for most schools.
- Quality cannot be imbibed in schools which have failed to bring disadvantaged children on par with the rest of the class. Most schools have still not been able to adopt an approach that strengthens inclusion and diversity.
- While infrastructure is a prerequisite for receiving boards affiliations, there is a general disconnect between utilisation of the resources and the utility of it in learning system. The challenge of the future lies in integrating state of the art infrastructure with the fundamental learning ecosystem.

Do's

- A good school must acknowledge the socio-economic inequities among its students but consciously make an effort to empower students coming from difficult circumstances. While assimilating these differences, the schools must also ensure that students learn to thrive and co-exist in a non-homogenous system. A school environment that fosters these differences, will also help students learn from these differences. Education must be tailored to suit the needs of a diverse set of minds, provide the care and instill faith. A school by way of targeted interventions and active supports can reduce the exclusion faced by socio-economically disadvantaged groups.
- For a school to perform well and achieve excellence, support from parents is an essential factor. Parents need to see education as an investment and not a burden. A school must form an association with parents, probably by way of active parent groups. This allows schools to develop interventions centered around parents. For instance, the Aga Khan group of schools, in order to reduce screen time for children, trained parents to deliver the educational content to their children.
- The incorporation of vocational training skills can help students develop attitudes such as dexterity and concentration. VET can be imparted as essential life skills.
- While most schools believe in inculcating values among their students, a school must have a coherent strategy to make learning a value laced experience. A good school must embed value in its teachings, have a specially designed program for the same and make an effort to monitor the percolation of a rich value system among its students.
- A good school must take semi-trained teachers, mentor and supervise them to curate a curriculum centered around children.
- A good school must have visionary leadership that is able to translate primary resources such as infrastructure and human resources into a centre of learning and growth.
- Technology in education is being explored by schools more so after the pandemic. A school is must provide technology solutions suited to the needs of the school. During the pandemic, several schools were able to transition to a digital platform. However, many of their students were without devices. Moreover, children in remote parts of the country had no access to education. While most schools are able to deploy technology in their teaching, a good school is one that is able to innovate a technological model to provide last-mile connectivity.

- A good school should allow students to pick, choose and learn at their own pace. Good quality becomes the culture when a school has good processes in place.
- Schools must focus on foundational learning. The gap between pre-primary and primary education needs to be bridged. Pre-primary education is largely unregulated, this often creates learning gaps and schools must intervene to iron them out.
- A school must focus on incorporating language skills, soft skills training, writing, and research skills in mainstream education practice.
- A good school uses extra-curricular activity to build team spirit and healthy competition among its students. • A school should prepare its student for the future and equip them with career guidance, so they're able to make the right choices after school.

Above all, a good school believes in the happiness of children and thus treats each child as an individual. Their systems are designed by the children and for the children. Satisfied children help institutions deliver results.

Don'ts

- Marks should not be taken as barometer of success. The school must see the progress of the child in terms of where they have come from and where they are now.
- Schools must stop treating students as a collective, and listen to children's need rather than telling them.
- Schools need to realise that technology cannot be deployed without taking into account the needs and constraints of the students. Smart boards seem widely popularised, it is important to ascertain whether actual learning and retention happen whilst using it.
- Schools must distance themselves from being solely focused on academic excellence and move towards creating leaders and human beings with exceptional life skills.
- While several schools believe that modern and premium infrastructure helps them attract students and retain them, it still does not guarantee quality in learning and education practices. An infrastructure-led cost heavy model must give way to one which pools or shares resources. Be it a playground, qualified teachers or a library if schools in a vicinity are able to share these resources, a far more sustainable, cost-effective and efficient approach can be developed.
- Moral values cannot and should not be treated as a school subject requiring separate classes, but rather be embedded in everyday learning and curriculum. Students must learn by doing rather than do by learning.
- Vocational education taught in school should not be done to lower expectations or as recourse to poor academic performance.
- A good school should not compromise on ethics.
- The failure of a school stems from the constant attention given to the best students while neglecting the weakest. A school should not solely focus on nurturing its best talent.
- A school cannot work only by fostering competition, what it needs to build is cooperation among its students and also teachers.
- A good school must avoid poor quality teachers.
- The focus of a school should not be on rote learning rather on knowledge creation.

Framework for Quality Education

- Enabling School Environment
 - Trained teachers
 - Early Childhood Care and Education
 - Technology in Education
 - Sports Development
 - Skill Development
- Enabling Policy Environment
 - Inclusion in school processes
 - Stakeholder engagement in policy-making processes
 - Pooling of infrastructure and resources
 - Streamlining Assessment and Curriculum practices
- Enabling Home and Community Environment
 - Parental Education
 - Values in education

- Parental Education
- Values in Education
- Inclusion in Society
- Cooperation over Competition

- Early Childhood
- Care and Education
- Skill Development
- Sports Development
- Trained Teachers
- Technology in Education
- Focus on the Weakest Students

- Stakeholder Engagement in policy-making Processes
- Pooling of Infrastructure and Resources
- Streamlining Assessment and Curriculum Practices

CENTRE FOR DEVELOPMENT POLICY AND PRACTICE (CDPP)

The Centre for Development Policy and Practice (CDPP) is a research institute that works on development concerns and contemporary public policy challenges.

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CDPP - GOVERNING COUNCIL

1. G. Sudhir is a former IAS officer. He was Chairman of the Commission of Inquiry to study the Socio-economic and Educational conditions of Muslims in Telangana.
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3. Neelima Khetan headed the CSR division for companies like Coca-Cola, the Vedanta Group and Hindustan Zinc Limited. She is now visiting fellow at Brookings India
4. Amitabh Kundu has been chairperson of the Post-Sachar Evaluation Committee set up by Ministry of Minority Affairs. Currently, he is chairs a Committee for Swachh Bharat Mission at the Ministry of Drinking Water and Sanitation.
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10. Rubina Mazhar is a social entrepreneur and Founder of SAFA. SAFA is a self-sustainable organisation working for the socio-economic upliftment of women.

CDPP - RESEARCH TEAM

1. G. Sudhir is Chairman of the Research Team at CDPP, and a former IAS officer.
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The CDPP brings out a monthly working paper based on the research work being carried out here. These are published on our website www.cdpp.co.in and sent to a select group for review, comments and critique.

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